

THE FACTOR OF FORMATION OF MEANING IN YOUTH IN THE CONDITIONS OF CREATING A NEW UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6991854>

Darmonov Aliyorbek Abdukhalilovich

*Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies
with the participation of the Department of "Humanities" assistant*

Abstract: *In the current conditions of globalization, when upheavals and social upheavals occur in various countries of the world, it is important from a socio-philosophical point of view to study the ideological principles of forming a sense of threat among the youth of Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *Renewal of Uzbekistan, youth of our country, resilience, vitality of youth, factors of sustainability, stability, security.*

Although all the peoples of the world wanted to be independent and follow their own path of independence, this did not happen to everyone. We know that independence is a very high responsibility, and its preservation, protection and strengthening is not an easy task, which can always be done on your own. In this regard, the change of time, period and region does not change the course of events, that is, the strengthening of independence in each period of the development of society is a moral factor in activity based on the same principles. As T. Fayzullaev noted, "from today's point of view, we must feel a great responsibility, but at the same time, an obligation. Therefore, the preservation and strengthening of independence is not an easy task, its burden is heavy. There are many examples in world history that, after gaining political independence, nations and countries fell into dependence on major powers that were unable to bear responsibility for independence [1].

In this regard, in certain transitional periods, specific social processes take place, political, economic, spiritual and educational systems change. During this period, an important task will be to maintain independence, ensure the sustainable development of the country and the formation of appropriate spiritual principles.

In general, it is known that the implementation of the tasks of the transitional period requires a certain amount of time. Undoubtedly, the fulfillment of these tasks requires purposefulness, perseverance and mobility from the members of society, initiative, perseverance and high courage

from leaders. During this period, independence will remain an unconditional condition for all reforms, achieving goals in the face of external and internal threats and resistance.

Analyzing the process of making a decision about a sense of threat among young people, we believe that, first of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to aspects that reflect the essence, definition and characteristics of this concept.

In this regard, we believe that the concept of "resilient youth" is, on the one hand, the timely awareness of various threats in life, the willingness to take a stand against ideas and practices that are different from others' and one's own, to resist or eliminate various threats. As the President said, "In such an ideological struggle, our youth must be sensitive and vigilant, and in all matters, first of all, act in the interests of the Motherland." [2] This means Secondly, this concept is the ability of a person to take into account not only his own thoughts and personal views, but also the opinions and views of others, to refuse, and not to force various forms of violence and threats as a means of communication. and conviction, to be equally demanding of others and of oneself. The peculiarity of adopting an opinion is that it recognizes and adheres to the right of everyone to be unique, does not prioritize personal inclinations and selfish attitudes, and respects the rights of others.

Emphasizing the need for reforms based on the traditions, values and mentality of the national statehood of our people, A. Erkayev said that the transformations in our country are based on the best world experience in reforming society. At the same time, he emphasizes the importance of the spiritual factor in working against various dangers for our society and population [3].

At the same time, external patterns that determine national factors in the formation of a sense of threat among young people in modern conditions of independence, of course, have an external basis associated with the specific status and responsibility of the country in the international plan. arena. In particular, the recognition of our country as an independent state in the international arena, as a result of which it has earned a worthy place in the world community, gained a high reputation, Uzbekistan has the right to vote in international relations, agreements with international organizations and countries on an equal footing. This is evidenced by the fact that that diplomatic, economic and cultural ties were established on the basis of treaties. In particular, observance and timely fulfillment of existing international obligations in accordance with the principle of

friendship and mutually beneficial cooperation with the peoples of the world and other countries, as well as strict adherence to the principles of the UN in foreign and domestic policy.

In this regard, in his speech at the UN General Assembly, President Mirziyoyev outlined the priorities of our country's policy in this direction: "Uzbekistan is ready for an open dialogue, while maintaining the status of a non-bloc. We are interested in expanding cooperation with all our partners in the name of peace, development and prosperity" [4].

The fact that today there is a movement for democratic renewal all over the world will certainly support our efforts to preserve our peaceful and serene life. However, striving to preserve our lives as the apple of our eye, we must resolutely resist the forces pursuing our selfish goals, geopolitical views.

Preservation and protection of sustainable development are, first of all, closely related to the necessary social protection of the human factor. If we look at the history of developed democratic societies, we will see that social protection was originally an important condition for social security.

In general, it is well known that any stage of renewal consists of a process of changes and reforms. At the same time, the further deepening of reforms, their coordination with the new level of development of society is a requirement of the time.

In order not to confuse the processes of the period of building a new Uzbekistan, it is necessary to have a certain force arising from the essence of any system and capable of directing these changes in one direction. If each system does not have a self-sustaining force capable of directing internal processes in a certain direction, then it will not be able to ensure the continuity of connections and connections between its constituent elements, and eventually disintegrates, self-destructs. The state performs the function of such a force that coordinates the existing elements of society, that is, the activities of various structures. In order not to confuse the processes of the period of building a new Uzbekistan, it is necessary to have a certain force arising from the essence of any system and capable of directing these changes in one direction. If each system does not have a self-sustaining force capable of directing internal processes in a certain direction, then it will not be able to ensure the continuity of connections and connections between its constituent elements, and eventually disintegrates, self-destructs. The state performs the function of such a force that coordinates the existing elements of society, that is, the activities of various structures. It is no coincidence that the head of our state, foreseeing

the course of events, has repeatedly said that "state bodies should serve the people" and is strengthening the legal framework in this regard.

Our state has for many years ensured the orderly implementation of the process of transition to a new society, and we have every reason to believe that it has fulfilled the task of reforming in accordance with the requirements of life. One of the reasons for this is the expansion of the powers of territorial bodies in the management system, the creation of opportunities for local self-government to resolve a number of issues on their own, without waiting for instructions "above". Even today, in the process of reforming economic relations, the state continues to support certain sections of society, in particular those in need of social protection, especially the younger generation [5].

In recent years, our government has adopted and implemented a number of state programs. At the same time, social support for our people has been identified as one of the main priorities. For example, today a significant part of the state budget is spent on the process of radical reform of the education system. The main part of these funds is aimed at creating and strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, which are completely new.

Many educational institutions are equipped with the latest equipment, computers and modern technical facilities. As a result, there is a sharp reduction in the number of people in need of social protection. This is the most important goal and result of a strong social policy. At the present stage of development of our country, the main direction and the final result of all reforms is the issue of population growth and taking into account the specific national values of our people.

All this, as an objective process, is greatly influenced by subjective factors, that is, all spiritual and educational changes, the renewal of the thinking of the population, especially the younger generation. Increasing the social activity of young people, encouraging their talents, talents and initiatives and helping them find their place in life [6]. As a result of such reforms, the current Strategy of Action for the Development of Uzbekistan is scientifically sound, meets the new development requirements and is resistant to crisis due to its powerful life potential. But this does not mean that all issues have been resolved, that there are no problems left. It is natural for life to propose new ones instead of the solved ones, and without this development is impossible.

It is concluded that the main goal of the ongoing reforms and historical transformations to build a new Uzbekistan is to ensure the consistent

development of our people, a democratic rule of law, a more prosperous civil society, life, dignity, rights and rights of our compatriots, to fully guarantee the freedom of the people and further enhance the image of our country in the international arena. This fact is confirmed by large-scale reforms taking place in our country, in all spheres of life.

The task is to deepen these reforms and bring up a worthy, harmonious and formidable generation. There is no doubt that the honest and selfless work of each of us is connected with the understanding of our responsibility in this direction.

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